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D1.4 – Project release of core applications

WP1: Software Scalability and Usability

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Executive Summary

This document describes the contents of the third project release (first in BioExcel-2), of software developed for the core applications in BioExcel. The efforts of Work Package 1 are spread over the entire project timeframe, and some collaborations, deployments or benchmarks might also use preliminary new code. However, to establish known benchmark baselines and provide reference versions of all codes used in the project (e.g. to integrate them in BioExcel workflows and use by other BioExcel teams), the Work Package also makes these formal code releases. This also comes with records describing the current status of the software that results from the planning, development, documentation, and testing processes. The release itself takes the form of a package of Open Source licensed source code, and can be downloaded from the BioExcel webpage at <http://bioexcel.eu/software/code-repositories>. For most of the codes this is a BioExcel-specific repository to sync the releases with other project needs, while general users are usually recommended to follow the documentation, download and installation instructions available on the normal application web pages.

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1 Introduction

BioExcel is driven by user impact. The core codes of the project have been selected from major European codes that are broadly used in life science applications, with a large number of high-impact scientific publications from independent users, and that are frequently used in PRACE/EuroHPC allocation requests. The CoE has additionally decided to focus on open source projects, in particular to make it possible for other users and developers to use the invested work to also benefit other applications. In particular, this means most development work (with some vendor co-design as an exception) can be tracked on a daily basis. All resulting features are also supported in at least annual major releases of the packages, where the BioExcel work is combined with substantial efforts from other sources.

In addition, to better track development and enable synchronization of new features e.g. for interfacing the codes, which might not match the normal development cycles, BioExcel also provides these project-specific releases of the source codes. This has the additional goal of enabling us to summarize and report the specific development resulting from the CoE efforts, and enable stakeholders such as the EC, compute centers and developers of related features or even users monitor the development process and/or provide feedback.

As part of BioExcel-2, the development process for all codes has moved to a significantly more user-driven feature request approach. These features are prioritized based on (1) periodic code surveys identifying the general parts to prioritize (such as GPU performance, or porting to new architectures), providing features that will enable new scientific applications, and not least requests for better documentation, user interfaces and interoperability. To ensure impact and efficiency, BioExcel will never completely fund development of any code - in particular the core scientific drivers should be secured with other competitive research grants, which is the case for all present applications. However, by focusing on integration, testing, maintenance and strategically important projects (such as enabling key European architectures), the CoE is both able to lift the technology readiness levels (TRL) to very mature scale (all the codes are now used in commercial settings, for instance) and provide larger impact both for European technology, infrastructure and scientific end users. The codes currently supported are selected based on their usage to study proteins, lipids, RNA, DNA, energy processes in cells, and in particular drug design applications requiring large-scale docking and free energy calculation:

- **GROMACS** is a high-performance task-parallel molecular dynamics software simulation and analysis suite. GROMACS is one of the most widely used biomolecular simulation codes in the world (accounting for some 5% of worldwide HPC time), and in particular in Europe, where it is one of the PRACE benchmark codes. The BioExcel work is focused on scaling and performance improvements, porting all acceleration to new Exascale hardware, as well as implementing modern techniques for modularization, documentation, code review and QA testing.
- **PMX** is a code for automatically preparing molecular topologies for advanced free energy calculations, which is a particularly important target for using massive amounts of molecular simulations both in academia and industry. This is a key factor in enabling researchers to automatically scan through and calculate free energy of binding for tens of thousands of compounds using MD

tools such as GROMACS.

- **HADDOCK** is an implementation of bio-molecular docking based on a wide range of biochemical information. This code has a very different usage profile, and it has been selected because of the importance of improving support for high-throughput life science calculations. HADDOCK is a key component of the many workflows developed in BioExcel. Its main mode of use is via its web portal.
- **CP2K** is a high-performance quantum chemistry application widely used in materials science, solid state physics and computational chemistry, and is a PRACE benchmark code. BioExcel has developed an interface that enables hybrid QM/MM simulation of biomolecular systems by coupling GROMACS to CP2K, thereby leveraging the latter's use of large-scale HPC resources for QM calculations, and is improving CP2K's QM/MM performance and scaling as part of a development roadmap to ready the coupled applications to efficiently exploit exascale resources. This work is underpinned by the creation and ongoing expansion of a public biomolecular QM/MM benchmark suite, which will also aid future CP2K development outside of BioExcel through its integration - along with BioExcel-developed code - into the canonical CP2K codebase, and which will contribute to PRACE benchmarking work where it is also planned to be used.

In addition to software development focused directly on the applications themselves, another important part of the usability improvements in BioExcel comes from integrating them into workflows as presented in work package 2.

The BioExcel codes have different degrees of parallelization maturity, and they have deliberately been selected to cover both the entire range of life science application needs as well as different challenges and approaches to make efficient usage of Exascale resources - ranging from extreme parallelism and low-level scaling through hardware co-design to massive big data and AI-driven problems where challenges are focused on handling millions of tasks and petabytes of data. This helps ensure the BioExcel project develops competence covering the entire scale of biomolecular modeling used in academia and industry, ranging from QM/MM models on the small atomic scale to simulations of very large systems and rapid integrative modeling, as well as disseminating technical competence to developers and users of new problem classes. The modifications implemented in the pilot codes, interoperability libraries, and related workflows facilitate using combinations of codes to solve application problems, which is particularly helped by the liberal open source licensing.

The contents of this release reflect the current status of the major ongoing effort of this work package on the pilot codes, covering the period subsequent to BioExcel-1 deliverable 1.4 (<https://zenodo.org/record/3563747>) and preceding the end of the first phase of the BioExcel project. This naturally encompasses the results of end-user consultation, team planning, software development, documentation, quality assurance, testing, and bug fixing that is expected for the output of a software e-infrastructure like BioExcel. The specification of software engineering and quality assurance were documented in BioExcel-2 deliverable D1.1 – Specification of software engineering and QA and the software roadmaps in BioExcel-2 deliverable D1.3 - Updated software roadmaps.

The project release is available from <http://bioexcel.eu/software/code-repositories> as a packaged source code archive for each of the three codes, as well as a convenience aggregate package (ALL_CODES). The documentation in this package provides references to the main repositories for the respective codes. The codes also provide extensive support and documentation, either through their existing web pages or fora such as the Bioexcel Discourse server at <http://ask.bioexcel.eu/>.

Although these BioExcel releases capture the improvements from BioExcel's effort, those changes have also been contributed back to each upstream project's code repository. Formally each pilot code's community manages their own formal releases separately and at different intervals. This is in line with the expectations of their existing user bases and different needs for release cycles, as the codes are developed by particular research groups and institutions supported by multiple streams of funding. However, for some of the codes (GROMACS, PMX, HADDOCK) BioExcel staff are co-responsible for the main management and steering of the software development.

The valuable support of BioExcel is acknowledged by each upstream project., BioExcel has also had major impact on teaching and tutorials, including both user- and developer-focused activities to improve software quality. Valuable feedback and input into the requirements gathering process are also collected via BioExcel and thus the CoE helps defining future priorities for the individual developer communities. As part of BioExcel-2 this is now also evident e.g. in the branding of the code support forums.

BioExcel is committed to business-friendly open source licensing for all code developed in the project, but to ensure impact for the most widely used application codes we also need to ensure the code can be used with existing code bases and their licenses. This is handled by making all BioExcel code available as independent libraries or scripts, which can easily be adapted to other codes too when more liberal licenses are available. The licenses used in BioExcel are the Lesser GNU General Public License (LGPL) v2.1 (GROMACS) , LGPL v3 (pmx) and the Apache License 2.0 (HADDOCK scripts, as well as WP2 workflows). These are all OSI-approved and well-recognized Open Source licenses that grant the right to run the code for any purpose, to link it into closed commercial applications, as well as to modify and/or redistribute the code. The licenses differ mainly in minor details such as restrictions on derived works or protections against software patent infringements.

While this particular deliverable describes the release of the project core applications, where we have a particular interest in pushing European technology and software, we also think scientific impact is best ensured through a broad user-focused view, and we believe our choices of e.g. inviting developers of other leading codes (AMBER, NAMD) to co-host tutorial and training sessions have been highly appreciated by end users.

2 GROMACS

For BioExcel 2, the GROMACS team has decided to have the BioExcel project releases coincide with GROMACS point releases. This main reason for this decision is to avoid confusion among users due to different types of GROMACS releases.. This project release of the GROMACS molecular simulation package corresponds to version 2020.2 of the official GROMACS release. Version 2020 incorporates many new features and improvements, most of which have been (co-)developed with resources from BioExcel.

2.1 Major features and improvements:

- **Density guided simulations:** Improvements and wider use of experimental techniques has lead to production of ever larger amounts of different types of “density-data” on bio-molecules. This data often contains information at atomistic length scales which is difficult to extract. Molecular dynamics simulations are becoming a standard tool for generating high-quality atomistic structures from density data. An important example is cryo-electron microscopy data, for which the Nobel prize in chemistry was awarded in 2017. GROMACS 2020 incorporates a 3D-density guided module that steers protein structures towards the experimental density. This is done using a thorough, Bayesian approach (not by simply pulling atoms locally towards regions of high density, as some other codes do). The computations needed for this fitting are rather expensive and we therefore implemented a multiple time-stepping approach, so the computational overhead is low.
- **Strongly improved free-energy performance:** Alchemical free-energy calculations are an important class of calculations for molecular dynamics in general and GROMACS in particular. Important use cases, especially in the pharmaceutical industry, are drug binding and protein mutation studies. Although the extra computational cost of mutating a few atoms is rather small compared to the total cost, this can lead to imbalances. When using GPUs, the non-bonded interactions involving mutated atoms remain on the CPU. When running (massively) parallel, the free-energy interactions are localized on a few ranks, as they are spatially localized. As the free-energy kernels were not SIMD optimized, they could significantly slow down the total computation. Now we SIMD optimized the free-energy kernels and templated them on several parameters to avoid conditionals. We have improved the performance of the kernels by a factor 2.5. This improves performance of free-energy runs on CPU+GPU machines by up to a factor 2.
- **Multi-GPU scaling through co-design** Through a year-long close collaboration with developer technology engineers from NVIDIA, this release of GROMACS comes with significantly improved general performance for accelerators, and in particular initial support for communicating directly between accelerators on a single node, without going over the PCIe bus or CPUs. This is still work in development, and some features are not yet enabled by default, but the resulting improved scaling can be highly impressive - several typical mid-range systems frequently studied in biology will now be able to use multiple accelerators in a node for a *single* simulation, with several-fold improved absolute performance. We expect this to also benefit

multi-node scaling and performance on all the pre-Exascale and Exascale systems, which is work in development for the second phase of BioExcel-2, as the pre-Exascale systems become available.

- **Modular integrator:** Ability to define Integration Loop based on individual small modules. The new modular integrator allows developers to implement new integration loops based on a small number of individual modules instead of using the legacy path. This makes it possible to design more user centric integration methods in an easy way.
- **“GPU-only” inner loop:** As graphical processing units (GPUs) are getting faster and the performance of CPUs is stagnating, the balance of computational power is shifting towards GPUs. To achieve optimal performance on GPU-heavy machines, more of the computation in GROMACS need to be shifted to GPUs. After moving the non-bonded forces, particle-mesh Ewald electrostatics and the bonded interactions, the main parts left on the CPU and integration and constraints. Although these are a relatively small part of the total computational cost, the GPU is idle when these parts are computed on the CPU. Furthermore, data needs to be transferred between CPU and GPU when using both. Although the computation itself is not difficult to port to the GPU, there is a lot of control logic, especially for different temperature and pressure coupling algorithms. In this release we have made all this work, which means the CPU is now only used for setup and pair-searching (which is done infrequently).
- **First release of the Python API:** Version 0.1 of the GROMACS Python API is included in this release. This allows managing complex simulations, data flow, and pluggable molecular dynamics extension code from Python. It also provides a Python interface to all GROMACS tools. This is a first version of the Python API, this API is planned to grow over the years to enable more flexible control of simulation setups and flows. This API is a central part of the exa-scale strategy of GROMACS, as it enable will enable ensemble parallelizm that is integrated with single simulation level parallelizm. A large amount of refactoring of internal GROMACS data structures was needed to achieve this.
- **Non-bonded kernel benchmark tool:** The kernel that takes more than half of the computational time in atomistic molecular simulations is the non-bonded interaction kernel. In GROMACS there are many flavors of these kernels, both in terms of functional shape and hardware targeted. For co-design projects and to enable vendors, centers and users to optimize kernel choices for the hardware, we have developed a benchmark tool in BioExcel. This tool times all supported types of kernels on the current hardware.

The (same) source code release is available on the BioExcel release page along with the other code, on www.gromacs.org and on Zenodo <https://zenodo.org/record/3773801>. The documentation for this release is available at <https://zenodo.org/record/3773799>.

3 PMX

Free energy calculations based on the first principles of statistical mechanics allow for high accuracy predictions of the changes in protein-ligand binding affinity, protein-protein interaction or protein stability upon amino acid mutation. Being able to estimate free energy differences is of particular interest for the scientific community both in academia and industry.

PMX based calculation setup in combination with the powerful molecular dynamics engine of Gromacs enables efficient utilisation of the largest European HPC centers. The non-equilibrium free energy calculation protocol supported by PMX and Gromacs is well parallelizable, requiring to perform a large number of independent simulations, thus ensuring linear scaling of the calculations.

The development of the PMX based alchemical free energy calculation framework within the scope of Bioexcel 2 comprises three major branches:

- implementing new features enhancing capabilities of the pmx software package;
- support, bug-fixes, facilitating usability of the free energy calculations with pmx and Gromacs;
- workflow development for convenient setup of alchemical free energy calculations.

3.1 New features

The PMX software package readily allows setting up alchemical calculations for amino acid, nucleic acid and arbitrary organic molecule modifications. All of the aforementioned setups are aimed at estimating relative free energy changes.

We have now additionally implemented support for preparing a simulation setup enabling *absolute* ligand-protein binding free energy calculations. The main new feature required by the absolute free energy calculation workflow is the need of a specific definition of restraints between the ligand and protein. pmx now provides a feature allowing to automate a generation of such a set of restraints, also providing a necessary analytical estimate of its contribution to the free energy.

Another commonly encountered challenge when performing alchemical free energy calculations is the proper treatment of annihilation/creation of a charge in the simulation box. An automated single-system-double-box setup implemented in pmx allows circumventing this issue by preparing the simulation box such that it remains neutral during the complete alchemical transformation.

A number of new features have been implemented to facilitate analysis of the results obtained from the non-equilibrium alchemical calculations. The PMX analysis module is now operating faster, allows input data slicing, enables block-based and bootstrapped uncertainty estimation, provides a convergence measure for the Bennett Acceptance Ratio estimator.

To further facilitate the analysis of the relative free energy calculations for the whole chemical libraries of compounds, a new method for cycle closure correction has been developed. The approach allows ensuring that the thermodynamic cycles constructed within the chemical library are properly closed. In contrast to the already available method for cycle closure correction [<http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/ct300911a>], the new approach is based on imposing the constraints already at the level of the free energy estimation. This way we have developed a first principles based constrained maximum

likelihood free energy estimator. In addition, an automated cycle identification feature was developed and implemented.

We have also implemented an alternative soft-core function into GROMACS, that allows avoiding artifacts in the non-equilibrium free energy calculations. This part of development is continued in collaboration with the GROMACS team.

3.2 Usability and continuous support

The PMX software was written in Python 2, the official support for which has ended with the beginning of 2020. To ensure long term usability of pmx we have started the process of porting the software to Python 3. Firstly, the core classes and modules have been adapted to support Python 3. Subsequently, the amino acid and nucleic acid mutation modules, as well as free energy analysis module were ported. The ligand modification module is currently the last part remaining to be made Python 3 compatible.

We have also kept pmx up-to-date with the latest version of the RDKit package, which allows performing atom mapping for ligand hybrid structure and topology generation.

A continuous support for pmx bug-fixes is provided. Some of the modules for which bug-fixes were needed over the Bioexcel 2 period include the topology, position restraint generation, as well as improving the schemes for maximum common substructure searches in ligand atom mapping.

3.3 Workflows

The main functionality of pmx is the preparation of hybrid structures/topologies for automated alchemical free energy calculations, allowing large-scale screens. Hence, the full workflow of setting up large sets of molecular dynamics simulations to calculate free energies is frequently desired by the end-user. Within the scope of Bioexcel 2 in collaboration with the Open Force Field consortium, we have started the development of workflows that would enable a convenient preparation, execution and analysis of the free energy calculations.

Currently, the first version of the ligand modification workflow for the relative binding affinity calculations is already prepared and being tested at Janssen pharmaceuticals. This development is complemented by the efforts of the IRB team within WP2 to further generalize and streamline the procedure of molecular simulation setup. In addition, a set of benchmark systems for protein-ligand relative free energy calculations was assembled and used to test the workflow.

Another workflow for amino acid mutations in calculating free energy changes in protein-protein binding is being developed to be applied in the use case for WP3.

4 HADDOCK

Here we present a bottom-up rewrite of HADDOCK which aims for its modularization allowing for the development of custom workflows. This new version, [HADDOCK v3.0](#) is being developed concurrently to the official [production version](#) (v2.4) and its [web portal](#). The HADDOCK docking protocol can be divided into four stages:

1. Rigid-body spatial search
2. Semi-flexible refinement
3. Final refinement (with or without explicit solvent)
4. Scoring.

In the current 2.4 version all these routines are deeply integrated as CNS scripts with high code dependency, running as one single workflow, which greatly hinders its expansion and incorporation into pipelines. Aiming towards a modular execution, the core routines (both at Python and CNS scripts levels) were refactored and divided into Python modules. The CNS execution was incorporated into the main code. This incorporation was done together with a new CNS-input composer module which provides more control over the CNS processes and eliminates the co-dependency between the stages, making them independent processes.

4.1 Introducing HADDOCK v3.0

This brand-new version was benchmarked using the Protein-Protein Benchmark v5.0 (github.com/haddock/BM5-clean) and compared in terms of CAPRI rankings over different subsets of HADDOCK generated complexes for both single structure and cluster-based rankings. This is done by comparing the predicted complex to its reference experimental structure. Benchmarking results showed that, upon refactoring of the CNS core routines, HADDOCK v3.0 has a similar to- or better performance than HADDOCK v2.4 (Figure 1). The first v3.0 version release has however limited functionalities compared to the production version (2.4) (see Supported restraints and limitations below).

	Single structure scoring						Cluster-based scoring			
	Top 1	Top 5	Top 10	Top 50	Top 100	Top 200	Top 1	Top 2	Top 5	Top 10
Acceptable irmsd ≤ 4 Å	151	177	182	195	200	208	155	187	204	204
	150	174	177	191	197	201	177	196	206	206
Medium irmsd ≤ 2 Å	89	97	99	102	104	108	98	115	120	120
	86	105	109	123	133	142	122	134	145	145
High irmsd ≤ 1 Å	18	20	20	20	21	21	24	28	29	29
	17	29	35	40	42	45	41	44	47	47

v 2.4
v 3.0

Figure 1: Benchmarking comparison of HADDOCK v3.0 against v2.4 using CAPRI metrics.

With this new modular approach, we aim at providing standalone routines to be later used in custom workflows. The current Alpha2 release (<https://www.bonvinlab.org/software/haddock3>) also introduces new features such as:

- **Continuous integration**
Unit and integration tests are continually being developed to ensure the code's sustainability and viability. Its continuous integration is implemented in a local server using Jenkins.
- **Setup and execution rework**
The setup and execution were simplified, removing the current two-step process required to run a docking simulation. Custom parameters and input files are given by the user via a single human-readable TOML file. Default parameters for each stage as well as the execution method are stored internally as a JSON configuration file. It currently has no support for HPC scheduling, and its default execution scheme is parallel via python's multiprocessing module.
- **Customizable CNS protocols**
Most of HADDOCK's protocols are executed via CNS (Crystallography & NMR System) scripts, which are used for various stages (e.g. the same CNS script handles the first two stages). A crucial step towards modularization was to remove these co-dependencies between stages, providing individual scripts for the execution of each stage. This change allows for the customization of the CNS protocols without affecting the global behaviour of all stages.
- **Supported restraints and limitations**
The current live version (v2.4) has support for many different restraints such as Cryo-EM, NMR residual dipolar coupling and pseudocontact shift restraints, and allows to use shape and coarse-grained representation of molecular systems. It supports the docking of up to 20 molecules, covering proteins, peptides, nucleic-acids and small ligands. The new modular 3.0 version still lacks many of those features and is only capable of handling a simplistic two body protein-protein scenario with ambiguous restraints.
- **Towards custom-made workflows**
The modularization of HADDOCK's core routines enables in the future the definition of custom workflows, making possible to swap or add execution steps, e.g.. changing the way rigid-body spatial search (e.g. the [LightDock](#) software whose further development is now occurring in Utrecht), or using a different algorithm for solvent-explicit refinement (e.g. connecting to Gromacs). An example of the default execution is provided in Figure 2.


```
main:

input, params = load_input_parameters('protein-protein.toml')

molecule_list = []
for mol in input['molecules']:
    clean_mol = PDB.process_input(mol)
    topology = CNS.generate_topology(clean_mol)
    molecule_list.append((clean_mol, topology))

rigidbody_comps = RigidBody(molecule_list, params).run()

selected_rigidbody_comps = PDB.select(rigidbody_comps, params)

semiflexible_comps = SemiFlexible(selected_rigidbody_comps, params).run()

waterref_comps = WaterRefinement(semiflexible_comps, params).run()

final_models, output_files = Analysis(waterref_comps, params).run()
```

Figure 2: HADDOCK 3.0.alpha2 Protein-Protein docking workflow and execution algorithm (pseudo-code).

- **Analysis integration:**

The analysis routines that calculate interface/ligand RMSDs, extract various energetic components and perform the clustering of the final models were ported from a collection of Python and shell scripts to the main HADDOCK v3.0 python framework as a module. Third-party software was incorporated in this step such as [Fastcontact](#), [Dcomplex](#) and [DockQ](#), which are integrated via python wrappers.

4.2 Toward exascale

Use Case 2 - High-throughput Modelling of Interactomes (D3.3 - Use case reports) aims to establish how reliable is the information that two given molecules actually interact with each other and how a complex network of connections can be extrapolated from it. These challenges are a highly complex computational task in the exa-scale level, requiring 1.7 Petabytes of data and approximately 10 Million computational hours. A thorough evaluation of HADDOCK is being conducted to identify bottlenecks and code limitations. As a first demonstration, the current live version of HADDOCK v2.4 has been containerized and a pre-exascale workflow was built in collaboration with PyCOMPSs team (D2.3 - First release of demonstration workflows).

The modelling of 49 complexes, was run as one single job orchestrated by PyCOMPS in the Marenostrum supercomputer using 50 nodes for a total of 2400 cores. Each complex took different times to be completed, ranging from 2 to 16 hours depending on the number of atoms of the input data. The total output data sums to 175GB or compressed archive.

Figure 3: Efficient usage of resources from the HADDOCK-PyCOMPSs workflow. Example of a single PyCOMPS/HADDOCK job executed on BSC Marenostrum using 50 nodes (2,400 cores).

We identified a few constraints such as the high volume of files being written in disk, high network traffic and no across node computation. These have been addressed in HADDOCK v2.4 source code and more rounds of the workflow are being executed. Since the development of HADDOCK v3.0 is concurrent to v2.4, these lessons can be directly applied to the new modular version.

In v2.4, job submission is managed by a wrapper built around a job scheduler (Torque/Slurm). Now it is possible to develop a custom-tailored submission machinery that can take full advantage of the computational resources directly into the source code, i.e. implementing PyCOMPSs directly into the source code. It also enables us to tackle the large I/O throughput intrinsic to HADDOCK (D1.2-IO Benchmark) by implementing from scratch a more robust file management protocol that can use metadata and hierarchical data formats.

This first BioExcel release of HADDOCK v3.0 is still very experimental and will evolve rapidly in the future. As such support will be rather limited for the time being, with the HADDOCK v2.4 version remaining for now the official production and fully supported version. The HADDOCK v3.0 code is freely available under [GitHub](https://github.com). Potential users are however encouraged to register at <https://www.bonvinlab.org/software/haddock3>.

5 QM/MM – GROMACS & CP2K

5.1 QM/MM interface between CP2K and GROMACS

Mechanistic insights into the catalytic action of enzymes is needed to understand how these proteins have evolved to mediate chemical reactivity. Also, for improving enzymes or designing new ones, detailed understanding of the underlying reaction mechanism is essential. Because the time and spatial resolutions are difficult to access experimentally, hybrid QM/MM simulation techniques, in which a small part of the system is modelled with a suitable level of ab initio or density functional theory (DFT) while the remainder is modelled with molecular mechanics force field, are the methods of choice to investigate enzyme reactivity. However, despite the simplicity of the QM/MM concept, the application is restricted to a small group of specialized users often using in-house codes. To unlock the power of QM/MM simulations for the whole biomolecular simulation community, we developed an interface between GROMACS and CP2K that, in contrast to previous QM/MM implementations, supports calculations under periodic boundary conditions with DFT methods. The following features have been implemented in GROMACS, are available for testing in an online repository located at <https://gitlab.com/aracsmd/gromacs/-/tree/CP2Kinterface>, and are due to be released as part of the upcoming GROMACS 2021 release:

- **The implementation of the GROMACS-CP2K interface** for performing fully-periodic QM/MM simulations has been developed between CP2K GROMACS 2020-dev and CP2K 6.1 packages. Through an extension module within the MdModules framework of GROMACS we maintain maximum code flexibility, while keeping the number of changes to the core to a minimum. Within the MdModules, the QM/MM interface has been implemented as an additional force provider. Thus, GROMACS is the main driver for QM/MM calculations, allowing users to effectively use standard input files and GROMACS system topologies to perform hybrid simulations. The CP2K library (libcp2k) that provides all routines needed for performing a QM/MM energy plus forces calculation is compiled separately and linked statically if the QM/MM option is switched on when the executables are built.
- **Topology modifications and automatized input generation.** To minimize the time and effort required to prepare a system for QM/MM simulations, we provided a user-friendly and straightforward input flow based on automatic input generation routines. These routines make the necessary modifications to the topology in the pre-processing phase of standard GROMACS input and provide validated CP2K parameters that should be suitable for biomolecular systems. Examples of such modifications to the topology that are now handled automatically are the placement of link atoms and the cancellation of spurious non-bonded and bonded forces interactions.
- **QM/MM simulations with temperature and pressure coupling.** To perform QM/MM MD simulation in the NPT ensemble we implemented in the interface and in CP2K itself a flexible cell approach to enable scaling of the QM box.
- **Parallel implementation.** The interface was implemented to work in all typical hardware execution contexts for GROMACS, and to support both single-node (with and without OpenMP) and multi-node configurations using MPI or hybrid MPI+OpenMP schemes. In addition, the interface supports both single and double precision versions of GROMACS.

5.2 QM/MM benchmark suite

BioExcel is providing the first release of its QM/MM benchmark suite, which contains benchmarks that exercise key QM/MM functionality within CP2K and use the GROMACS-CP2K interface newly developed by the project:

https://github.com/bioexcel/qmmm_benchmark_suite

The suite is used within the project to profile and optimise CP2K and GROMACS+CP2K performance and scalability and to test the functionality and usability of the GROMACS-CP2K interface. The benchmark suite will promote long-term future testing, development and optimisation of CP2K for biomolecular systems as it has been incorporated directly into the canonical CP2K codebase (see <https://github.com/cp2k/cp2k/tree/9a1d529ad0508d7de5b856979efefbfd93892c4>), and it will also be used to perform CP2K benchmarking as part of PRACE application enabling activities.

As well as underpinning the project's QM/MM development work, the benchmark suite is being used to build up a body of knowledge on best practice running QM/MM simulations using CP2K and GROMACS+CP2K on a range of different platforms. This is feeding into the project's support and training activities, and will be made available to the community as a best practice guide to help maximise scientific impact of the project and enhance usage of HPC resources with these applications.

The benchmarks have been selected to include a range of different types of biomolecular systems, system sizes (in terms of both number of MM and QM atoms), and QM treatment parameters such as basis set and exchange/correlation energy functional. The benchmark suite will be expanded on an ongoing basis after this initial release to include a greater variety of biomolecular systems with larger QM subsystems, including systems drawn from BioExcel Use Case work and to ensure the suite reflects the range of systems reported to be of interest in an online community survey regarding QM/MM for biomolecular modelling and simulation.

This first release of the benchmark suite includes QM/MM simulation inputs for four biological systems as summarised in Table 1. These were chosen to include a variety of systems, including some related to the BioExcel use cases, and a range of system sizes with regard to both total number of atoms and number of atoms treated quantum mechanically, with the largest so far consisting of 253 QM atoms. In all cases CP2K's Gaussian and Plane Wave (GPW) method is used for the QM subsystem, and the Gaussian Expansion of the Electrostatic Potential (GEEP) method used to compute QM/MM energies and forces [1][2]. We have made sure to include systems modelled with both PBE and BLYP exchange-correlation (XC) energy functionals. The DZVP-MOLOPT-GTH basis set is selected for most of the systems. Pseudopotentials are chosen in accordance with the choice of functional, for which each is specifically optimised. In most cases the system is treated periodically, however we have made sure to include a non-periodic case as the GEEP potential is then calculated using different variants of the QM/MM subroutines. Detailed descriptions of each of the biomolecular benchmark systems are provided in the benchmark suite repository linked above.

Name	Type	QM atoms	Total atoms	DFT Functional	DFT Basis set	MD run type	Periodic?
MQAE	solute- solvent	34	16,396	BLYP	DZVP-MOLOPT-GTH	NVE	Y
CIC	ion channel	19, 253	150,925	BLYP	DZVP-MOLOPT-GTH	NVE	Y
CBD PHY	phytochrome	68	167,922	PBE	DZVP-MOLOPT-GTH	NVE	Y
GFP ScaleQM	fluorescent protein	20, 32, 53, 77	28,264	BLYP	DZVP-GTH-BLYP	NVT	N

Table 1: Summary of the first release of the BioExcel QM/MM benchmark suite. Detailed descriptions of the biomolecular systems and benchmark inputs are provided in the benchmark suite repository

5.2.1 Execution scenarios

For each system the suite contains three different benchmarks, corresponding to different execution scenarios, namely:

- CP2K QM/MM MD
- CP2K QM/MM kernel
- GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM MD

CP2K QM/MM molecular dynamics

These benchmarks consist of a short QM/MM MD simulation for each system using CP2K. For each system 5 MD steps are performed with a time step of 1 fs. The benchmarks can each be run with the standard release version of CP2K. For each system the CP2K input file (.inp), the initial input coordinates (.pdb) and the Amber MM forcefield (.prmtop) are provided

CP2K QM/MM kernel

These benchmark the performance of the QM/MM kernel described in deliverable D1.2, which computes the force contribution due to the long-range part of the QM/MM potential. As described in D1.2, it and closely related routines are large contributors to overall CP2K QM/MM simulation runtime hence its isolation in a kernel facilitates

performance analysis and optimisation. As many of the QM/MM subroutines have a similar structure, optimisations made to the kernel are tested and evaluated before implementation into related routines.

The version of the QM/MM kernel included in the benchmark suite includes OpenMP threading optimisations implemented by BioExcel, the effect of which is reported in section 5.3 of this deliverable.

GROMACS+CP2K QM/MM molecular dynamics

These benchmark GROMACS used jointly with CP2K for performing a QM/MM MD simulation using the newly developed interface. For each benchmark all the required input files, namely the topology file (.top), the configuration file (.gro), the MD parameters file (grompp.mdp) and the index (.ndx) file, are provided. To ensure as much consistency as possible between each GROMACS+CP2K benchmark and its CP2K standalone benchmark equivalent, the Amber forcefields used in each CP2K benchmark were converted into GROMACS format using ParmEd (<https://github.com/ParmEd/ParmEd>). The benchmarks are set up to perform 5 MD steps, with a time step of 1 fs.

5.3 Optimisation of CP2K QM/MM subroutines

The CP2K subroutines responsible for computing QM/MM forces and energies using the GEEP algorithm [1][2] were previously identified as responsible for a significant fraction of runtime. These subroutines were therefore targets for optimisation to improve performance and scaling for CP2K, and thereby the same for overall QM/MM simulation using GROMACS+CP2K, since the cost of the QM treatment typically far exceeds the cost of MM calculations and dominates overall runtime.

CP2K implements multi-node parallelism through MPI and supports hybrid MPI+OpenMP execution. The presence of multiple OpenMP threads per MPI rank can yield better performance using a given number of cores, or indeed allow some simulations to run at all on a given HPC system by reducing per-node memory requirements through enhanced usage of shared memory.

OpenMP-based multithreading was not present in any of the CP2K QM/MM subroutines, so we have added OpenMP to these routines in order to provide a way to gain performance running QM/MM simulations with MPI+OpenMP. The additional runtime flexibility thanks to hybrid parallel execution can be used to tune for optimal performance on a range of existing and future HPC platforms with different memory/cache layouts and hierarchies.

The efficiency of our implementation was confirmed by running the CP2K QM/MM kernel benchmarks from the BioExcel QM/MM benchmark suite described in section 5.2. Parallel efficiency for one case is shown in Figure 4 and remains above 95% as the number of threads is increased, demonstrating excellent subroutine-level efficiency of the OpenMP implementation. Broadly similar results were observed across the range of benchmark systems.

Figure 4: Parallel efficiency of the CP2K QM/MM kernel for the CBD_PHY benchmark with multithreading after addition of OpenMP. Error bars are shown but are too small to be visible outside the data points.

Despite the strong inherent subroutine-level efficiency of the implemented optimisations, it is typical of CP2K performance in general that when the application executes on a fixed number of cores with MPI+OpenMP as opposed to pure MPI much of the theoretical performance increase from multithreading may be offset by the reduction in overall number of MPI ranks, and overall performance gain therefore limited due to the parts of CP2K that have not been parallelised with OpenMP. To evaluate the impact of our optimisations on real usage of CP2K for biomolecular QM/MM simulation we investigated performance of CP2K QM/MM MD benchmarks from the BioExcel QM/MM benchmark suite.

The time per MD step was recorded for hybrid MPI+OpenMP-parallel execution of CP2K for different combinations of MPI ranks and threads per rank for each given number of nodes on the ARCHER supercomputer (a CRAY XC30 machine with two 12-core Intel Xeon E5-2697 v2 processors and 64GB memory per node).

In some cases MPI+OpenMP-parallel execution was indeed found to offer little performance benefit over running with pure MPI or a single thread per rank, in particular for benchmarks with small QM subsystems (< 30 QM atoms), such as the CIC-19 benchmark. For benchmarks with larger QM subsystems, including for MQAE (34 QM atoms) and CBD_PHY (68 QM atoms), using 6 threads per rank was shown to give best performance running on 10 nodes (240 cores) and 16 nodes (384 cores) respectively, with a bigger impact for CBD_PHY – see Figure 5. For the GFP_ScaleQM system (77 QM atoms), which differs from the other benchmark in that it calls the non-periodic versions of the QM/MM GEEP routines, using 6 threads per rank also yielded best performance when running on 6 or more nodes.

Figure 5: Speed up per MD step for the BioExcel CBD_PHY benchmark using CP2K v7.1 with added OpenMP optimisation of QM/MM subroutines, running on ARCHER. “X TH” implies CP2K executes with X threads per MPI rank, with the total number of MPI ranks chosen so that all cores on each node are used. Error bars are shown but are too small to be visible outside the data points.

For QM subsystems beyond a certain size the user is ultimately forced due to memory constraints to switch from CP2K’s default ATOM parallel decomposition scheme, which requires a significant amount of memory since the grid is replicated on each process, to the alternative GRID parallel scheme, which parallelises over grid slices and replicates the QM atoms. For example, the CIC-253 benchmark contains the largest QM subsystem (253 QM atoms) considered so far in the BioExcel QM/MM benchmarking suite. Due to the large number of QM atoms and the size of the QM region, using CP2K’s default ATOM parallel decomposition scheme was found to be too large on the machine used (ARCHER, 64GB per node) even when running on 10 nodes, requiring use of the GRID scheme.

A severe load imbalance strongly limiting overall performance and scaling was observed in the original unoptimised QM/MM subroutines under the GRID scheme. This can be seen in Figure 6, showing that the difference between the MPI rank with largest execution time per MD step (MAX) and the average time per step across all ranks (AVE) for any number of nodes is large. In fact the MAX time remains constant regardless of number of ranks, limiting overall scaling. This is reflected in Figure 7, showing no speed up at all of the MAX rank.

Figure 6: Maximum (MAX) and average (AVE) rank execution times for a single call of the CP2K QM/MM subroutines `qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG` and `qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG` that takes place during a single MD step. Error bars are shown but are too small to be visible outside the data points.

Figure 7: Speed up of the MAX and AVE ranks for a single call of the CP2K QM/MM subroutines `qmmm_forces_with_gaussian_LG` and `qmmm_elec_with_gaussian_LG` that takes place during a single MD step.

As can be seen in Figure 8, our OpenMP optimisations of the QM/MM subroutines improve performance and scaling by removing some of this load imbalance, as it enables work in the MAX rank to be shared at least amongst threads. Speedup was found to increase with additional threads per rank up to 6 threads, **achieving roughly a factor 2.5 improvement**, with less benefit for more than 6 threads per rank.

Figure 8: The effect of CP2K QM/MM threading optimisations on speed up per MD step for CIC-253. Error bars are shown but are too small to be visible outside the data points.

References

- [1] An Efficient Real Space Multigrid QM/MM Electrostatic Coupling. Laino, T.; Mohamed, F.; Laio, A.; Parrinello, M. J. Chem. Theory Comput. 2005, 1, 1176-1184. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ct050123f>
- [2] An Efficient Linear-Scaling Electrostatic Coupling for Treating Periodic Boundary Conditions in QM/MM Simulations. Laino, T.; Mohamed, F. Laio, A. and Parrinello, M. J. Chem. Theory Comput. 2006 2 (5), 1370-1378 <https://doi.org/10.1021/ct6001169>

5.4 Exascale readiness

Achieving pre-exascale performance for hybrid QM/MM simulations is possible with chain-of-states techniques, in which paths through phase space connecting reactants to products are automatically optimized and transition states are located. Because these techniques are based on simultaneous simulation of a very large number of copies of the system, scaling is intrinsically linear. We are therefore implementing one such approach, namely the Nudge Elastic Band method, into GROMACS.

Having improved performance of QM/MM simulation with CP2K by a significant factor (**2X-3X**) for simulations involving large QM subsystems, BioExcel is investigating the feasibility of further alleviating the newly identified underlying load imbalance associated with CP2K's GRID-based parallel decomposition scheme. Ensuring work is shared more evenly amongst ranks should have a significant impact on the ability to efficiently scale QM/MM simulations with large QM subsystems to more than the hundreds of cores identified here.

Other planned work to improve QM/MM performance already described in the BioExcel-2 software development roadmap deliverable D1.3 is also expected to benefit performance and extend efficient scaling out to larger numbers of nodes. For example GPU acceleration of QM/MM subroutines, which was already planned to be developed with CP2K's default ATOM-based parallel decomposition in mind, also offers a potential solution to the abovementioned GRID-based load imbalance by providing a powerful way to speed up the work currently executed on the MAX rank or indeed a subset of all ranks with high-load.

To clarify the pathway to exascale readiness for QM/MM biomolecular simulation using GROMACS+CP2K via the interface it is worth restating that the impact of QM/MM optimisations already done and still planned for standalone CP2K mostly carry across to the joint performance of the coupled applications.